

LEGAL REGULATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN THE FIELD OF CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract: This article examines the necessity and essence of legal regulation of environmental protection in the field of construction. The article discusses various regulations governing construction activities to minimize environmental impact and ensure sustainable development. The article shows the role of state bodies, legislation and enforcement mechanisms in compliance with environmental protection standards in construction projects.

Key words: legal protection, environment, construction, laws, standards.

INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is at the crossroads of growth and sustainability. Because the demand for infrastructure development collides with the need to protect the environment. In such a dynamic landscape, the legal regulation of environmental protection in construction has emerged as an important basis for harmonizing these conflicting interests and ensuring that development is carried out in harmony with nature.¹

MAIN PART

The legal framework for environmental protection in construction includes a wide range of laws and regulations at the local, national and international levels. In many countries, Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is the primary tool for assessing the potential environmental consequences of construction projects before they are approved. These assessments examine factors such as air and water quality, biodiversity and impacts on local communities to help identify and mitigate potential environmental risks.

Our Constitution, which is our main encyclopedia, defines the basic rules of Uzbekistan's ecological development strategy, requirements for ecological and ecological safety of the population, and this political-legal document contains the most important and basic rules for the protection of the natural environment and the use of natural resources in our country. determines.

¹ Kibert, Charles J., Jan Sendzimir, and Brad Guy. "Construction ecology and metabolism: natural system analogues for a sustainable built environment." *Construction Management & Economics* 18, no. 8 (2000): 903-916.

It is known that the role and importance of constitutional norms in the implementation of environmental policy is incomparable. It is in the Basic Law that the basic principles of the formation of environmental activities of state bodies and public associations are strengthened, the environmental duties of citizens are determined, priority directions of ecologically sustainable development of society are established, etc.

The system of constitutional norms can be conditionally divided into two parts - general and special ecological norms, based on the description of social relations that arise and are regulated during the interaction of society and nature.

General constitutional norms are of urgent importance in the establishment of a democratic-legal state and civil society, in determining the basic principles of organizing the activities of state authorities and management bodies, in guaranteeing the basic rights and freedoms of citizens, and in strengthening environmental law and order.

Territory and parts of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, territories and parts of the territories of settlements, state and regional systems of population settlement, land plots, buildings and structures, territorial production, urban development and landscape complexes, recreation and production zones, cultural heritage areas facilities and their protection zones, water areas on the borders of settlements and inter-settlement areas, engineering and transport communications, advertising and information facilities (constructions) are the objects of urban development.² Construction projects are subject to numerous environmental regulations governing everything from waste management and pollution control to noise and vibration levels. These regulations often set strict environmental standards and require developers to implement environmental protection measures during and after construction.³

In Uzbekistan, urban planning works are carried out in close connection with the issues of environmental protection, protection of citizens from natural and man-made conditions, and protection of public health. These rules are enshrined in the Urban Development Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is known that the negative impact of construction can occur at all its stages - from the acquisition of building materials to the use of finished objects. As a result of the release of dust, soot, and harmful gases into the environment during the

² <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5307951>

³ Bellamy Foster, John, and Brett Clark. "The sociology of ecology: ecological organism versus ecosystem ecology in the social construction of ecological science, 1926-1935." *Organization & Environment* 21, no. 3 (2008): 311-352.

production of construction materials, products and details, it causes air pollution and has a negative impact on human health. In this case, construction work requires a significant increase in environmental culture, and these aspects impose equal responsibility not only on construction organizations, but also on customer and design organizations. In planning and construction projects, it is necessary to reflect the protection of atmospheric air from harmful emissions emitted by construction and transport vehicles and many other environmental measures. Nature protection measures must also be taken when demolishing buildings and structures.

In recent years, due to concerns about climate change and resource depletion, there has been an increased focus on sustainable development in the construction industry. Sustainable construction seeks to minimize the environmental impact of buildings and infrastructure by incorporating principles of energy efficiency, water conservation and waste reduction into the design and construction process.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection" of December 9, 1992, "Methodological rules" must be taken into account. Therefore, the following must pass the State ecological examination:

- drafts of state programs, concepts, the main directions and development schemes of the national economy's productive forces and networks;
- site selection materials for all types of construction, pre-plan, pre-project and project documents;
- programs of research works related to the assessment of the state of natural resources and their use;
- environmental situation in individual regions, population centers and facilities;
- existing enterprises and other objects that have a negative impact on the state of the surrounding natural environment.

Green building practices such as using environmentally friendly materials, improving energy efficiency and optimizing water use are becoming increasingly popular in the construction industry. Many countries have adopted green building codes and certification programs that encourage developers to build in an environmentally responsible manner. Of course, ecological expertise plays a decisive role in the prevention of negative effects on the natural environment and public health, environmental inconveniences, and in making decisions regarding the conduct of any economic activity. When evaluating projects considered as objects of ecological expertise, special attention should be paid to

environmental stability, factors affecting the health and life of the population. As one of the important principles of ecological expertise, the direct participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations, the public and citizens in this process ensures that environmental expertise is transparent and fair. In accordance with the requirements of ecological standards and regulations, it is required to carry out nature protection measures in any construction, regardless of the danger category of the object. That is, elimination of emissions released into the atmosphere as a result of construction or their cleaning, prevention of loss of natural resources are among them.

Ensuring compliance with environmental protection regulations in the construction industry is a complex and multifaceted process. State agencies responsible for monitoring environmental protection may conduct inspections, issue permits, and impose penalties for violations of environmental laws. In some cases, developers may be required to repair environmental damage caused by their projects or to compensate affected communities for environmental damage.

Compliance with environmental regulations is essential to protect the environment and ensure that construction projects are carried out in a sustainable manner. However, enforcement can be difficult due to the complexity of environmental regulations, the diversity of construction projects, and the need to balance environmental protection with economic development.

CONCLUSION

Legal regulation of environmental protection in the field of construction plays a decisive role in promoting sustainable development and ensuring the implementation of construction projects in an environmentally responsible manner. By setting clear standards for environmental impacts, conducting thorough environmental impact assessments, and ensuring compliance with environmental regulations, governments can mitigate the environmental impact of construction activities and protect the natural world for future generations.⁴ It is essential that stakeholders in the construction industry adopt sustainable practices and work with regulators to protect the environment and promote sustainable development. Only through a concerted effort to balance economic growth with environmental stewardship will we be able to build a more sustainable future for our planet.

⁴ Escobar, Arturo. "Construction nature: Elements for a post-structuralist political ecology." *Futures* 28, no. 4 (1996): 325-343.

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